

Guide for Peer Assessment in Oral Presentations

EMI Version – *English as a Medium of Instruction*

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Role-playing and Peer Assessment for the Integration of Professional
Competences for Employability in Chemistry Studies (JOAQUIM)

Emerging Educational Innovation Project (PIEE) at the University of Valencia

Burjassot, July 2025

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Images on pages 6, 10, 12–16, and 19 were generated using artificial intelligence via ChatGPT (OpenAI), July 2025.

Presentation

Beyond the academic knowledge specific to the field, the final years of undergraduate studies—and especially master's programs—should prepare students for their imminent entry into the job market and promote the development of critical thinking skills. In the case of Chemistry studies, this preparation should include not only technical and industry-specific content (such as legislation, marketing, or safety), but also the so-called transversal competences or soft skills, which are essential for professional practice.

The JOAQUIM project's main objective is to integrate these types of practical professional competences into the training of students in the final years of Chemistry programs.

Peer assessment—based on expert judgement, as commonly applied in the review of scientific publications or project evaluations—is also a widespread practice in professional environments, especially in contexts such as recruitment, promotion, or teamwork. Therefore, developing the ability to assess critically and responsibly is an essential skill for future educators and any professional.

In this context, we have incorporated peer or cross-assessment as part of the final assessment in several senior-year courses, with a reduced weight and always under faculty supervision. This peer evaluation takes place within the framework of an activity that simulates an academic conference at the end of the semester, in which students—working in pairs or small groups—deliver oral presentations to their classmates. In addition to conventional assessment by the teaching staff, a peer assessment phase is included to foster critical reflection, engagement with learning, and the development of communication skills.

This document presents a short guide for implementing this activity, intending to make it available to fellow instructors who may wish to adapt or incorporate it into their teaching contexts.

Importance of Peer Assessment

1. Peer assessment transforms the traditional role of students, who **move from being passive recipients** of grades to becoming **active agents** in processes of analyzing and evaluating knowledge.
2. This practice promotes **autonomy** and **metacognition**, as it requires students to justify their judgments and to identify strengths and areas for improvement in both their peers' work and their own work.
3. From a teaching perspective, peer assessment opens up opportunities to design **more participatory learning scenarios**, with richer interaction between students and content.
4. The incorporation of peer assessment mechanisms allows progress toward **more formative assessment models**, shifting away from mere grade allocation.
5. In terms of educational innovation, the systematic and reflective use of peer assessment contributes to building **a more transparent, interactive, coherent, and competence-based assessment culture**.
6. Introducing peer assessment in academic settings helps develop **transferable skills for the workplace**, thus enhancing students' employability in sectors demanding teamwork, shared leadership, and peer review.

Relevance of Peer Assessment

From the framework of **Bloom's taxonomy**, peer assessment enables the development of higher-order cognitive skills such as analyzing, evaluating, and creating, going beyond mere understanding or recall of content.

By participating in peer assessment processes, students not only apply knowledge but also reinterpret and reformulate it, thereby activating skills that belong to the highest levels of critical thinking, according to Bloom.

Cognitive Levels Addressed Through Different Teaching Activities

Development of the Activity

1. We propose a **fictional conference on a topic related to the course content** (e.g., “Applications of Polymers and Colloids in the Context of Sustainability”).
2. Students are divided **into groups of 2 or 3 people** to make the activity feasible within the scheduled time and encourage cooperative work.
3. Each group proposes in advance, according to the planned timeline, **a topic of their choice**, on which they must deliver a **12-minute oral presentation**. All team members must speak for a similar amount of time. The instructors prepare the conference program and schedule of presentations. After each presentation, there is a **question-and-answer session** lasting about 10 minutes, which also includes critical feedback by the instructors.

► The times can be adjusted as needed.

Development of the Activity

4. The oral presentations are part of the continuous assessment and represent **a specific percentage of the final grade** (in our particular case, in a 4th-year elective of the Chemistry degree, they accounted for 15% of the final grade).
5. The presentations are assessed using **an assessment rubric** (identical for both instructors and students). Our proposed scoring system (with a maximum of 132 points) is presented in the corresponding section of this guide. There are three components in the assessment:
 - i. **Assessment by the instructors.**
 - ii. **Peer assessment by fellow students.**
 - iii. **"Assessment of the assessment"**: evaluation by the instructors of the assessments carried out by the students. This step ensures oversight and fairness in the evaluation process, allowing instructors to address any inconsistencies. If any irregularity is detected in a group's peer assessment, the instructors may intervene accordingly.
6. To organize the task and the assessments, the **"Workshop" tool in Moodle** will be used. This tool allows student evaluations to be carried out online through the virtual classroom. In addition to the numerical score, students will be required to provide **a brief written feedback on the group being assessed**. Students will evaluate all other groups individually (although they may consult with their group members if they wish), but not their own group.

For practical reasons, it is proposed that students assess the groups as a whole across all items of the rubric. In contrast, instructors will assess some items (e.g., oral delivery) on an individual basis.

Example of a Seminar Program

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Polymers & Colloids

SEMINAR OF PRESENTATIONS ON APPLICATIONS OF POLYMERS AND COLLOIDS

Graduation Hall ("Saló de Graus") of the Faculty of Chemistry
April 25–26 – 5.30 p.m. to 7.30 p.m.

	<u>Presenting Team</u>	<u>Title of presentation</u>
Tuesday, April 25th		
5:25 pm		<i>Opening and Introductory Explanations</i>
5:30 pm	BAD	Polymers in Formula 1
6:00 pm	<i>The Brownian Boys</i>	Polymers in Batteries
6:30 pm	<i>The Number One</i>	Polymers and Colloids in Nail Polish
7:00 pm	<i>PoliAJA</i>	Bioabsorbable Polymers in Surgical Sutures
Wednesday, April 26th		
5:30 pm	<i>Radius</i>	Polymers in F1 Tires
6:00 pm	<i>IP</i>	Polypyrrole in Artificial Nerves and Muscles
6:30 pm	<i>GOOD</i>	Polymers in Contact Lenses
7:00 pm	<i>RMA</i>	Polymers in LEGO

Example of a seminar program organized following the instructions of this guide for the elective course Polymers and Colloids in the Degree in Chemistry (4th year).

Instructions for Using the Rubric

- Each of the **seven rubric items** is scored from **0 to 4** (or 1 to 4). However, for the final item (“question round”), the score assigned by the students is straightforward (up to 4 points), whereas the teachers’ score is multiplied by 2 (i.e., a maximum of 8 points). As a result, the maximum total score from students’ evaluations is 28 points, while the teachers’ evaluation can reach up to 32 points.
- Teachers are allowed to award half points (e.g., 3.5 instead of just 3 or 4), whereas students cannot, since their evaluations are submitted electronically via the Moodle rubric tool, which only allows whole numbers.
- One risk of this type of rubric is the reluctance to award maximum scores, which can severely penalize students. The difference between a score of 3 out of 4 (75%) and 4 out of 4 (100%) is quite significant. Therefore, we encourage teachers to be aware that it is valid to award a score of 4 when appropriate, and not to reserve it solely for “perfection.”

Proposed Assessment Rubric

CRITERION	INSUFFICIENT (0 – 1 points)	ACCEPTABLE (2 points)	GOOD LEVEL (3 points)	VERY GOOD (4 points)	POINTS
Contents and structure of the presentation					
(1) Choice of the topic and contents of the presentation	The choice of the topic is poor. The title does not fit the exposed contents. Poor contents. Information mostly reproduced from other sources, without reworking. Important aspects of the topic are missing.	Although the topic is appropriate, the title does not fit the content or creates false expectations. In general, proper contents, but not nicely elaborated. A relevant aspect is missing, but the overall presentation is acceptable.	Original and interesting topic. Title adjusted to the contents. In general, the contents match the topic and are well treated. A section of the presentation may be missing or incomplete.	Original and interesting topic. Title adjusted to the contents. The contents are complete and correspond perfectly to the topic. Topic treated in an attractive and professional manner.	
(2) Structure: presence of introduction, exposition and synthesis	Poor and unclear structure. There is no logical sequence in the information. Missing introduction or summary/conclusion section.	Adequate sections, but confusing structure in certain moments. Lack of clear connections between the parts. At least one important element is missing from the structure.	Correct structure, with few development errors. At some point, a better transition between one idea and another may be missing.	Well-defined sections. Presentation structured in a clear and understandable way. Logical and effective transitions between topics. Clear conclusion.	
Rhythm and speech (teachers evaluate individually, students evaluate the group as a whole)					
(3) Rhythm and speech	The speech does not sound natural. Inappropriate intonation and rhythm. Almost all the content is read. Language not appropriate to the formal communicative environment.	The speech is not as natural as it should be. The rhythm and intonation could be improved. The student reads part of the presentation, but the message is conveyed correctly.	The speech sounds quite natural, without major errors and with good rhythm and intonation. The explanations are mostly accurate.	Very natural speech and proper pronunciation, intonation and rhythm. Precise and correct explanations.	
Formal aspects					
(4) Format of the slides and graphics	Absence of careful formal treatment along the presentation. Significant and systematic formatting errors (e.g., too much information, too small font). Few graphics and superfluous materials.	The presentation is acceptable, but not much formally worked. Major formatting errors (e.g., too much information, font size), but the effort is appreciated. Graphic materials acceptable, but sometimes superfluous.	The presentation is neat and visually attractive, but has some minor formal errors. Correct use of animations. In general, the materials are adequate and help to understand the concepts.	Clear presentation, visually attractive and with an optimal formal organization. There are no formal errors or, if any, the errors are irrelevant. Effective animations. Interesting and attractive graphic and support materials.	
(5) Language correction in slides	The slides contain many typos or serious misspellings or wrong expressions.	In general, the language used is acceptable, but there are quite a few typographical or expression errors.	The language used is correct. Minor expression errors or some very sporadic typographical error.	Careful language, without errors. The presentation has been revised several times to avoid typographical errors.	
(6) Information sources	The sources of information and the origin of the graphics are not documented.	Few (or none) references from reliable sources (scientific journals and books). Only Internet and Wikipedia. Some sources are not documented and many are not in the proper format.	Most of the information sources are reliable (scientific journals and books). Documented information sources, but in some cases the format is not correct or the references do not appear in the right place.	There are enough reliable references (scientific journals or books). All sources of information and origin of graphics are documented and in the correct format.	
Round of questions (teachers evaluate individually, students evaluate the group as a whole)					
(7) Question round [IT SCORES DOUBLE in case of the teachers]	The student does not answer the questions.	The student tries to answer, but some of the arguments are not correct. There are important misconceptions.	Correct answers or, at least, well argued. There are no serious misconceptions.	All the answers are correct and well argued.	___ x 2

Example of a Scoring Grid

Simplified scoring sheet to facilitate note-taking during oral presentations, intended for use by both teachers and students.

	Topic and contents	Structure	Speech	Format	Language	References	Questions			
Group 1	Student 1									
	Student 2									
	Student 3									
Group 2	Student 4									
	Student 5									
	Student 6									
Group 3	Student 7									
	Student 8									
	Student 9									

Proposed Distribution of Scores

We propose a scoring system totaling 132 points, distributed as follows:

	Points	Percentage
Scoring by teachers	$3 \times 32 = 96$	73%
Scoring by students	28	21%
“Assessment of the assessment” (by teachers)	8	6%
TOTAL	132	100%

The **initial score awarded by the teachers**, out of 32 points, is **multiplied by 3**, so that the teachers’ carries a weight of over 70%.

This scoring gives peer assessment a value slightly above 20%.

Implementation in Moodle

The use of the “Workshop” tool in Moodle is proposed to implement the peer assessment task.

Phase 1: Workshop Setup

In this phase, the teaching staff defines the key parameters of the workshop: setting the title and description of the activity, setting the rubric or assessment guide, determining the number of peer reviews per student, and establishing the timeline for the different phases.

2024-25 Polymers and colloids Gr.A-T (36462) / Sections / Final Presentations about Applications / Presentation Workshop

Presentation Workshop

Workshop Settings Assessment form Submissions allocation More ▾

Submissions closed: Tuesday, 6 May 2025, 9:00 AM
Assessments closed: Friday, 9 May 2025, 11:59 PM

Setup phase

Setup phase Current phase ●	Submission phase Switch to the submission phase ○	Assessment phase Switch to the assessment phase ○	Grading evaluation phase Switch to the evaluation phase ○	Closed Close workshop ○
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Set the workshop description ✓ Provide instructions for submission ✓ Edit assessment form ✗ Switch to the next phase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Provide instructions for assessment ✓ Allocate submissions expected: 16 submitted: 4 to allocate: 0 ⌚ Submissions deadline: Tuesday, 6 May 2025, 9:00 AM (79 days ago) ⌚ Late submissions are allowed ⌚ Time restrictions do not apply to you 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⌚ Assessment deadline: Friday, 9 May 2025, 11:59 PM (75 days ago) ⌚ Time restrictions do not apply to you 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Calculate submission grades expected: 16 calculated: 4 ✗ Calculate assessment grades expected: 16 calculated: 11 ✗ Provide a conclusion of the activity 	

Description ▾

Space to upload your presentations and evaluate those of your colleagues.

- Presentations must be uploaded (only one per group) before **9:00 a.m. on Tuesday, May 6th**.
- The evaluations of your classmates, which will stick to the rubric posted in the virtual classroom, can be discussed and agreed with your group colleagues (it is not mandatory), but in the end you have to do them individually. The evaluations will be carried out once they have finished, but before **Friday May 9 at 11:59 p.m.**

Implementation in Moodle

Phase 2: Submission Phase

In this phase, the groups have to submit their presentation, following the instructions and criteria established by the teachers.

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Ppt Presentation Workshop

Workshop Settings Assessment form Submissions allocation More ▾

Submissions closed: Tuesday, 6 May 2025, 9:00 AM
Assessments closed: Friday, 9 May 2025, 11:59 PM

Submission phase

Setup phase Switch to the setup phase ○	Submission phase Current phase ●	Assessment phase Switch to the assessment phase ○	Grading evaluation phase Switch to the evaluation phase ○	Closed Close workshop ○
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Set the workshop description ✓ Provide instructions for submission ✓ Edit assessment form 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Provide instructions for assessment ✓ Allocate submissions expected: 16 submitted: 4 to allocate: 0 ⓘ There is at least one author who has not yet submitted their work ⓘ Submissions deadline: Tuesday, 6 May 2025, 9:00 AM (79 days ago) ⓘ Late submissions are allowed ⓘ Time restrictions do not apply to you ✓ Switch to the next phase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⓘ Assessment deadline: Friday, 9 May 2025, 11:59 PM (75 days ago) ⓘ Time restrictions do not apply to you 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Calculate submission grades expected: 16 calculated: 4 ✓ Calculate assessment grades expected: 16 calculated: 11 ✓ Provide a conclusion of the activity 	

Instructions for submission ▾

Presentations must be uploaded (only one per group) before **9:00 a.m. on Tuesday, May 6th**.

Presentations will be uploaded in PDF, PPTX or ODP format. Although the PDF format is allowed, it is recommended to use Power Point or LibreOffice Impress for presentations, since they allow animations and more visual resources. If any group prefers to use other applications, ask the professor beforehand.

Implementation in Moodle

Phase 3: Assessment Phase

In this phase, after the oral presentations, students assess the performance of their peers using the provided rubric. This assessment is carried out online through the Moodle platform.

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Presentation Workshop

Workshop Settings Assessment form Submissions allocation More ▾

Submissions closed: Tuesday, 6 May 2025, 9:00 AM
Assessments closed: Friday, 9 May 2025, 11:59 PM

Assessment phase

Setup phase	Submission phase	Assessment phase	Grading evaluation phase	Closed
Switch to the setup phase <input type="radio"/> ✓ Set the workshop description ✓ Provide instructions for submission ✓ Edit assessment form	Switch to the submission phase <input type="radio"/> ✓ Provide instructions for assessment ✓ Allocate submissions expected: 16 submitted: 4 to allocate: 0 ⓘ There is at least one author who has not yet submitted their work ⓘ Submissions deadline: Tuesday, 6 May 2025, 9:00 AM (79 days ago) ⓘ Late submissions are allowed ⓘ Time restrictions do not apply to you	Current phase ● ⓘ Assessment deadline: Friday, 9 May 2025, 11:59 PM (75 days ago) ⓘ Time restrictions do not apply to you ✓ Switch to the next phase	Switch to the evaluation phase <input type="radio"/> ✓ Calculate submission grades expected: 16 calculated: 4 ✓ Calculate assessment grades expected: 16 calculated: 11 ✓ Provide a conclusion of the activity	Close workshop <input type="radio"/>

Workshop grades report ▾

Visible groups: All participants ▾

First name: All A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z

Implementation in Moodle

Phase 4: Grading Evaluation Phase

In this final phase, the teachers review the peer assessments conducted by the students and assess the quality of the evaluations provided. This grading acknowledges the students' effort and responsibility in assessing their peers and helps ensure the fairness of the assessment system.

Based on our experience, we recommend that the teachers manually adjust the automatic grades assigned by Moodle algorithm, as the automatic system is strictly based on how much a student's score deviates from the average.

The screenshot shows the Moodle Workshop settings interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: Workshop, Settings, Assessment form, Submissions allocation, and More. Below this, it indicates 'Submissions closed: Tuesday, 6 May 2025, 9:00 AM' and 'Assessments closed: Friday, 9 May 2025, 11:59 PM'. The main section is titled 'Grading evaluation phase'. It contains five columns of settings:

- Setup phase:** Switch to the setup phase. Includes: Set the workshop description, Provide instructions for submission, Edit assessment form.
- Submission phase:** Switch to the submission phase. Includes: Provide instructions for assessment, Allocate submissions (submitted: 4, to allocate: 0). Warnings: 'There is at least one author who has not yet submitted their work', 'Submissions deadline: Tuesday, 6 May 2025, 9:00 AM (79 days ago)', 'Late submissions are allowed', 'Time restrictions do not apply to you'.
- Assessment phase:** Switch to the assessment phase. Includes: 'Assessment deadline: Friday, 9 May 2025, 11:59 PM (75 days ago)', 'Time restrictions do not apply to you'.
- Grading evaluation phase:** Current phase. Includes: 'Calculate submission grades' (expected: 16, calculated: 4), 'Calculate assessment grades' (expected: 16, calculated: 11), 'Provide a conclusion of the activity' (marked with a red X), 'Switch to the next phase'.
- Closed:** Close workshop.

Below the columns, the 'Grading evaluation method' is set to 'Comparison with the best assessment'. Under 'Grading evaluation settings', 'Comparison of assessments' is set to 'very lax'. A 'Re-calculate grades' button is visible at the bottom.

Concluding Remarks

1. Peer assessment is not only an evaluation tool but also a learning strategy that promotes responsibility, critical reflection, and active student engagement.
2. When properly designed and guided, it contributes to improving both the quality of learning and the collaborative culture within the classroom.
3. This practice reinforces transparency and understanding of assessment criteria, which are key aspects for promoting fairer and more meaningful processes.
4. From an instructional perspective, peer assessment represents an opportunity for methodological innovation and a reconsideration of the traditional evaluation role.
5. Moreover, it helps prepare students for real professional environments, where peer feedback, joint review, and shared evaluation are essential components of daily work.
6. Implementing peer assessment involves challenges—such as prior training, defining clear rubrics, or managing potential biases—but the educational and competency-related gains are substantial.
7. Ultimately, peer assessment is a way to educate in values such as responsibility, collaboration, and critical thinking, which are essential for academic life and civic participation.

“feedback should cause thinking. It should be focused; it should relate to the learning goals that have been shared with the students; and it should be more work for the recipient than the donor. Indeed, the whole purpose of feedback should be to increase the extent to which students are owners of their own learning,”

“The first fundamental principle of effective classroom feedback is that feedback should be more work for the recipient than the donor.”

Dylan Wiliam (2017)
Embedded Formative Assessment (2nd ed.)
Bloomington, MN: Solution Tree Press.

PEER REVIEW

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